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Research Article

**AWARENESS OF THE PATIENTS ABOUT THE PREDISPOSING
FACTORS OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION IN SAUDI ARABIA**¹Alaa Rashed Mohamed Adam¹BA degree, faculty of medicine, Almaarefa University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.**Abstract:**

Background: cardiovascular diseases is currently the major source of death in the developing countries especially in Saudi Arabia due to low activity, bad food habits, smoking and obesity.

Objectives: This study was performed to assess patient's awareness to factors precipitating myocardial infarction (MI) in Saudi Arabia.

Patients and Methods: This cross – sectional study included 280 individual who filled an Electronic Questionnaire about the patient's knowledge about the factors precipitating myocardial infarction

Results: According to the survey taken, there are many precipitating factors of myocardial infarction as: sex, where it is more in men than in women and 84% of the individuals were aware of it. Overweight, 81% of subjects aware of it. Consumption of high starch and saturated fatty acids foods, 92.9% of subjects aware of it. High blood pressure, 81.6% of subjects aware of it. Diabetes, 40% of subjects aware of it. Depression for long duration, 50% of the subjects were aware of it. Decreased physical activity and sedentary life, 81.1% of the individuals were aware of it. Smoking, 83.3% of the individuals were aware of it.

Conclusion: our study revealed that the average awareness of an out- patient about myocardial infarction causes is good enough, but most of the patients are unaware about how other medical problems as diabetes, elevated blood pressure, and depression are related to myocardial infarction.

Keywords: awareness, cardio-vascular, infarction, myocardial.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular disease is currently a major source of death in the developing countries especially in Saudi Arabia. The rates of deaths due to cardio-vascular problems have increased in these countries over the last three decades. This rise is due to exaggeration of risk factors of CVDs in these areas, also it reflects lack of population strategies for prevention and health care. [1]

Factors precipitating Cardiovascular diseases include : age , common above 50 years however it may take place at younger ages , sex : more prevalent in males than females, hypertension , diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, cigarette smoking, excess body weight, and sedentary lifestyle, stress, depression for long duration. [2]

Symptoms of myocardial infarction vary from silent MI (i.e. no or mild pain) to Severe chest pain. The main symptom usually is severe chest pain which for longer than 15 minutes and may continue for hours. This pain may be referred to the jaw, across the left arm, or both arms. Pain may be associated with sweating, fainting, Large MI may cause immediate collapse and death. [3]

So increased awareness and perception of factors precipitating cardiovascular diseases and its symptoms is an important step in their prevention.

Patients and methods:

Study design:

Site of study: This study was carried out in Saudi Arabia

Type of study: cross- sectional questionnaire -based study

Subjects: general population in Saudi Arabia fulfilling the inclusion criteria

Sample size: this study included 280 individual of general population

Sample collection technique:

The subjects of study were selected by Electronic questionnaire

Inclusion criteria:

- 1-general sane population in Saudi Arabia.
- 2-diabetics or hypertensive or obese individuals
- 3- Age: between 15-60 year

4-individuals who agreed to accomplish the questionnaire

Exclusion criteria:

- 1-individuals from outside Saudi Arabia
- 2- Age less than 15 years
- 3- Doctors and nurses
- 4- Individuals who didn't agree to accomplish the questionnaire.

Questionnaire design and validation:

The questionnaire was created following wide search. It was initially developed in English language then translated into Arabic language

The questionnaire was constructed to include:

- Age
- Sex
- If the subject know what is myocardial infarction
- Has any chronic disease (diabetes , hypertension , heart disease)
- If the subject is aware of factors precipitating MI(hypertension ,DM, overweight ,sedentary life and low physical activity ,smoking and depression)

DATA COLLECTION: -

Quantitative Data Collection method using - administering surveys with close question

Statistics and data analysis: After gathering the data, it was analyzed by SPSS. The results were presented in figures as frequencies and percentages.

Ethics: Before to filling the Electronic questionnaire, a written agreement was taken from each participating individual, confidentiality of the information was promised and maintained.

RESULTS:

Our study included 280 individual who agreed to fill the questionnaire and

Analysis of collected data showed the following results:

Figure 1: Bar chart representing frequency of people who don't know what exactly myocardial infarction (A) is, and those who know well what is it. (B) and frequency of those who know whether it affects people below 40 years.

Figure 2: Bar chart represent frequency of people who know that MI affect males more than females and whether overweight is a precipitating factor for MI or not?

The results of our survey showed that 58.2% of the individuals knew what myocardial infarction is, individuals younger than 40 years old are also liable to myocardial infarction and over 50% of the individuals are aware of it as in **figure 1**.

MI are more common in males than in females and 84% of the individuals were aware of it. People who are overweight have higher probability to get myocardial infarction than the others who have a normal weight and 81.1% of the individuals were aware of it as in **figure 2**.

Figure 3: Bar chart represent frequency of individuals who know that consumption of diet with high levels of starch and saturated fatty acids and elevated blood pressure lead to myocardial infarction

Consumption of starch and saturated fatty acids rich food can be another leading cause for myocardial infarction, 92.9% of the individuals were aware of it. Hypertension is a cause for myocardial infarction but only 81.6% of the individuals were aware of it as in **figure 3**.

Figure 4: Bar chart representing frequency of individuals who know that Diabetes and Depression for long duration lead to myocardial infarction.

Diabetes is an important factor which leads to myocardial infarction and only 43% of the individuals were aware of it. Depression for long duration can lead to myocardial infarction and only 50% of the individuals were aware of it.as in **Figure 4**.

Figure 5: Bar chart representing frequency of individuals who know that sedentary life and smoking are precipitating factors for myocardial infarction.

Regular exercise can partly prevent myocardial infarction and low physical activity and sedentary life can increase risk of myocardial infarction but only 81.1% of the individuals were aware of it. Smoking can be a precipitating factor of myocardial infarction and only 83.3% of the individuals were aware of it as in **figure 5**.

DISCUSSION:

According to institute of health measurement and evaluation, IHD represent 20 % of deaths in 2016 in Saudi Arabia. So, we have assessed the degree of knowledge of general population in Saudi Arabia as a step for advancement of health care programs where increase awareness of these precipitating factors will decrease Myocardial infarction cases.

Results of our study revealed that 58% of the involved individuals scored the overall understanding of what exactly the meaning of myocardial infarction as in **figure 1** but 42% don't know what does it mean. This is quite similar to percentage detected in UAE by *Khan, N.S* [4] which was 52.8%. .our percentage was more than that of people in South Africa, where *Surka s* [5]. Studies reported that less than 50% of individuals have good knowledge about MI.

Our study revealed that 84% of individuals are aware that MI is more common in men than women.

Also revealed that 81.1% are aware that overweight is a precipitating factor for MI as in **figure 2**. This percentage is more than that of Nakibuuka *J* [6] whose results showed that <10% of participants identified obesity as a CVD risk factor. This result is quite similar to *Awad A*, [7] results in Kuwait that showed 86.4% of participants are aware of obesity as a precipitating factor for cardio-vascular disease .This high knowledge resulted from marked representation of obesity and health programs in mass media.

Our study revealed that 92.9% of individuals know that Consumption of starch and saturated fatty acids rich food can be another inducing factor for myocardial infarction, this result is less than that detected by *Komolafe MA* [8] whose results revealed that 99.1% of participants are aware of bad habits of food consumption is a precipitating factor for cardio-vascular disease and higher than that of *Awad A* [7], results in Kuwait (85.8%). This indicates high awareness about unhealthy food.

And also revealed that 81.6 % of individuals know that hypertension is a precipitating factor for myocardial infarction as in **figure 3**. This percentage is higher than that of South Africa according to

Surka s [5], *Boateng* [9] results that showed that 0 % the respondents cited hypertension as a precipitating factor of cardio – vascular disease, also higher than that of *Awad A* [7] results in Kuwait (64.3%). And quite similar to that of *Martsevich* [10] whose results revealed that Patients tend to be more aware of arterial hypertension (80.3% women; 75% men) as a precipitating factor for cardio-vascular disease .

Our study results showed that 43% of individuals are aware that DM is a risk factor for MI which is quite similar to *Komolafe* [8] whose results that 47.4% among secondary school teachers in Nigeria are aware about DM as a risk factor for cardio-vascular disease and lower than *Awad A* [7] results in Kuwait (64.3%).

Also revealed that only 50% of individuals are aware that depression for long duration is a precipitating factor for MI.as in **figure 4**

Our study results revealed that 81.1% of individuals are aware that physical inactivity and sedentary life are precipitating factors for MI. This percentage is higher than that detected by *Komolafe MA* [8] whose results showed only 57% of participants in Nigeria are aware of physical inactivity as a precipitating factor for cardio-vascular disease. And similar to *Awad A* [7] results in Kuwait (83.7%).

Also revealed that 83.3% of individuals are aware that smoking is a precipitating factor for MI as in **figure 5**. This percentage is higher than that detected by Mohammed *J*. [11] whose results revealed that 70.6% among military personnel in Nigeria are aware of smoking as a precipitating factor for cardio-vascular disease and less than *Awad A*, [7] results in Kuwait (88.7%).

CONCLUSION:

The analysis of our data showed that the average awareness of an outpatient about MI and its risk factors, is good for some extent, but most of the patients are unaware about how other medical problems like diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and depression are related to myocardial infarction. So , more health care programs and campaigns are required to increase awareness about MI and its risk factors as myocardial infarction has become more prominent in Saudi Arabia .It can be partly reduced if awareness can be created about its predisposing factors and if the patients are educated about it.

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Figures legend:

Figure 1	Bar chart representing frequency of people who don't know what is exactly myocardial infarction (A), and those who know well what is it. (B) and frequency of those who know whether it affects people below 40 years.
Figure 2	Bar chart represent frequency of people who know that MI affect males more than females and whether overweight is risk factor for MI or not?
Figure 3	Bar chart represent frequency of individuals who know that consumption of diet with high levels of starch and saturated fatty acids and elevated blood pressure lead to myocardial infarction
Figure 4	Bar chart representing frequency of individuals who know that Diabetes and Depression over long periods lead to myocardial infarction.
Figure 5	Bar chart representing frequency of individuals who know that sedentary life and smoking are risk factors for myocardial infarction.